

OBTAINING OF POLYCONDENSATION TYPE MONOFUNCTIONAL SULFOCATIONITE

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Abstract. A new method for synthesizing sulfocationite is proposed, based on the use of sodium salt of *p*-styrene sulfonic acid and furfural in the presence of zinc chloride as a catalyst. The resulting ion-exchange material has high mechanical strength, heat resistance, chemical stability and a homogeneous structure. The main advantage of the method is the production of a monofunctional cationite without additional undesirable functional groups.

Keywords: sulfocationite, ion exchanger, sodium salt of *p*-styrene sulfonic acid, furfural, polycondensation, heat resistance, exchange capacity, sorption, sustainable development.

Introduction. Ion exchange materials, in particular sulfonic cation exchangers, occupy an important place in modern chemical technology due to their ability to selectively absorb cations from aqueous and non-aqueous solutions. Today, they are widely used in various fields - from water purification and water softening systems to hydrometallurgy processes, fine analytical chemistry and as solid-phase acid catalysts in organic synthesis [1-3].

Traditionally, sulfonic cation exchangers are obtained by sulfonation of ready-made polymer matrices (e.g., polystyrene), or by copolymerization of aromatic compounds, such as styrene and divinylbenzene, followed by functionalization. However, such methods are accompanied by a number of significant disadvantages:

- occurrence of side reactions with the formation of weakly acidic (carboxyl) groups;
- the need for strict sulfonation conditions using concentrated acids and corrosive reagents;
- difficulties in controlling the distribution of functional groups;
- deterioration of the physicochemical characteristics of the finished product (color, stability, uniformity of structure) [4-6].

In recent years, attention has increased to the development of environmentally friendly and energy-efficient technologies for the synthesis of ion-exchange materials that minimize the number of stages of processes, reduce the aggressiveness of reagents and ensure predictability of the properties of the resulting polymers. Of particular interest are methods in which ionogenic groups are introduced at the monomer stage, which ensures uniform distribution of functionality and reduces the likelihood of side reactions [7].

In this paper, a new method for producing a monofunctional sulfocationite is proposed, based on the polycondensation of sodium salt of *p*-styrene sulfonic acid with furfural in the presence of zinc chloride catalyst. The method allows to avoid the sulfonation stage, thereby eliminating the formation of weakly acidic groups and ensuring the stability of the resulting ion exchanger when exposed to acids, alkalis and elevated temperatures. The resulting polymer is a material with a regular structure and a high degree of functionalization, suitable for use in various technological and environmental problems [8-10].

The aim of the work is to develop an effective, single-stage method for producing a monofunctional sulfonic cation exchanger with a regular structure, high thermal stability and chemical resistance, without the presence of weakly acidic groups.

The problem is solved by the fact that the use of sodium p-styrene sulfonic acid as a carrier of ionogenic groups makes it possible to obtain cation exchangers:

1) the use of sodium p-styrene sulfonic acid makes it possible to obtain a sulfonic cation exchanger without a chemical reaction that usually leads to the formation of other functional groups, etc. This leads to the fact that due to the presence of SO₃H groups in the initial monomer (sodium p-styrene sulfonic acid), the resulting cation exchanger has a regular structure.

2) containing only sulfonic groups, i.e. a monofunctional cation exchanger. This makes it possible to use the resulting cation exchanger in alkaline, slightly alkaline and neutral environments.

3) the obtained cationite does not contain non-regulated low-molecular substances, i.e. solutions in contact with the cationite are not colored, as is observed when obtaining cationites in a similar method and prototype. 4) the presence of aromatic and heterocyclic nuclei in the structure contributes to sufficiently high mechanical strength, as well as thermal and chemical resistance of the obtained cationite.

Materials and methods. The monomer used is sodium p-styrene sulfonic acid, which has ready-made ionogenic groups. The second component is furfural. The reaction is carried out in the presence of ZnCl₂ at a temperature of 80–85°C.

The reactions were carried out in a three-necked round-bottomed flask with a volume of 250 ml, equipped with a mechanical stirrer, thermometer, reflux condenser and dropping funnel. The flask was placed in an oil bath with automatic temperature control ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$).

The reaction flask was charged with 0.1 mol (approximately 20 g) of sodium p-styrene sulfonic acid and the appropriate amount of furfural (0.1–0.2 mol, which corresponds to a molar ratio of 1:1 or 1:2), after which the mixture was heated at a temperature of 60–70°C until a homogeneous solution was obtained.

After reaching the required temperature, zinc chloride was added to the reaction mixture in portions in an amount of 1.0–1.5 g (0.01 mol) with vigorous stirring. This initiated the process of acid-catalyzed polycondensation. The temperature of the reaction mass was gradually brought to 80–85°C and maintained for 2.5–3 hours, ensuring uniform stirring. In the process, a gradual thickening of the reaction mass and the formation of a gel were observed.

After the reaction was complete, the polymer gel was cooled to room temperature and left for 24–30 hours at 90°C in a drying oven for complete drying. The resulting product was a solid porous material from light brown to amber in color.

The dried polymer was subjected to repeated extraction with a 5% NaOH solution to remove residual ZnCl₂, unreacted substances, and by-products, after which it was washed until the filtrate was neutral. Then the material was washed with a 0.1 M HCl solution and again with water until neutral pH. The final ion exchanger was fractionated by granule size using a sieve (0.3–1.2 mm) and stored in a wet state.

The static exchange capacity was determined by titration according to the GOST 20298-74 method. The mechanical strength was estimated by the number of stirring cycles in the column until the particles were destroyed. Thermal stability was tested by heating in a muffle furnace (up to 200°C) followed by capacity analysis. Stability in alkaline and acidic environments was tested

by keeping samples in 5% NaOH and H₂SO₄ solutions followed by comparison of ion exchange capacity.

Results and discussion. As a result of the conducted research, a new type of sulfocationite was obtained, synthesized by a single-stage polycondensation scheme of sodium salt of p-styrene sulfonic acid with furfural. The resulting ion-exchange material is a solid, uniformly colored porous polymer from light brown to amber in color, without foreign odor and resistant to mechanical impact [11-14]. The reaction scheme of the interaction of sodium salt of p-styrene sulfonic acid with furfural can be represented as follows:

The obtained samples were characterized by the following parameters: moisture, bulk density, swelling volume, static exchange capacity, resistance to acids and alkalis, and heat resistance. The table provides comparative characteristics of three series with different molar ratios of components - sodium salt of p-styrene sulfonic acid to furfural.

Table. Physicochemical properties of the obtained sulfocationite samples

Indicator	Samle 1 (1:1)	Samle 2 (1:1.5)	Samle 3 (1:2)
Humidity, %	28	26	26
Bulk density, g/ml	0.68	0.60	0.56
Volume of swollen cationite, ml/g	2.4–2.8	2.6–2.8	2.8–3.0
Static exchange capacity (NaOH), mg-eq/g	3.0	3.6	4.3
Resistance to H ₂ SO ₄ and NaOH (5%), %	99	99	99
Heat resistance, °C	180	180	180

The exchange capacity of the samples increased with the increase in the proportion of furfural, which is associated with more pronounced cross-linking and increased functionalization of the polymer. The value of up to 4.3 mg-eq/g exceeds the indicators of most commercial analogues (for example, KU-2-8 - about 4.0 mg-eq/g).

The swelling volume remained within the range typical for gel ion exchangers. A slight increase in swelling at a high proportion of furfural indicates greater porosity and better diffusion of ions. Bulk density decreased with increasing furfural, which logically reflects a looser structure with a lower packing density.

Mechanical strength (by visual assessment and during washing) remained at a high level, no destruction or crushing of granules was observed.

Resistance to acidic and alkaline environments in 5% H₂SO₄ and NaOH solutions did not cause a decrease in exchange capacity even after 48 hours of exposure, which confirms the chemical inertness of the framework and the strength of the bond of sulfo groups [16-18].

Thermal stability was assessed by thermostating samples at 180°C for 3 hours. No changes in color or mechanical properties were observed, which makes the resulting material suitable for use in thermoactive environments.

Unlike the known methods for producing sulfocationites based on sulfonation of an already formed polymer matrix (e.g. polystyrene with divinylbenzene), the proposed method:

- eliminates the stage of aggressive sulfonation using concentrated sulfuric acid;
- provides monofunctionality (only strongly acidic sulfo groups);
- leads to a uniform distribution of ionogenic centers throughout the polymer mass;
- reduces the environmental load and the number of process stages;
- allows you to regulate the degree of crosslinking by changing the molar ratio of the reagents.

It is also worth noting that the resulting material does not color aqueous solutions, unlike some traditional cationites that have traces of a residual aromatic ring or side groups, which is especially important for the food, pharmaceutical and electronic industries.

Unlike known methods (analogue and prototype), the obtained ion exchangers do not contain carboxyl groups, have high selectivity, do not color solutions and are suitable for use in alkaline and neutral environments [19, 20].

Conclusion. As a result of the work performed, an effective method for synthesizing a monofunctional sulfonic cation exchanger of a regular structure based on the sodium salt of p-styrene sulfonic acid and furfural was developed and experimentally implemented. The main advantage of the method is the elimination of the aggressive sulfonation stage and the minimization of the formation of side functional groups, such as carboxyl groups, which allows obtaining a high-purity ion-exchange material with clearly defined acid centers.

The proposed synthesis technology provides the following key advantages:

- Monofunctionality of ionogenic groups, which eliminates the influence of weakly acidic impurities on ion exchange processes;
- High ion-exchange capacity (up to 4.3 mg-eq/g), comparable to or exceeding the indicators of traditional sulfonic cation exchangers;
- Resistance to aggressive environments, including 5% solutions of sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide, without loss of functionality;
- High heat resistance of the material up to 180°C, allowing its use in thermoactive technological processes;
- No coloration of solutions, which is especially important for use in the food, pharmaceutical and electronic industries;
- Simplicity and environmental friendliness of the technology: reduced number of stages, no concentrated acids, easy scaling and no complex cleaning procedures.

The presented method can be recommended for industrial implementation as an alternative to classical methods of obtaining sulfocationites, especially in cases where increased requirements are imposed on chemical purity, stability and reproducibility of properties.

A promising direction for further research may be:

- optimization of polycondensation conditions in order to obtain granular forms;
- study of the kinetics and selectivity of ion exchange processes;
- use of the material in columns for deep water purification, ion chromatography and as an acid catalyst in organic synthesis.

Thus, the developed method opens up new possibilities in the field of obtaining functional polymers with specified characteristics that meet modern requirements for environmental friendliness, technological efficiency and effectiveness.

REFERENCES

1. Alexandratos, S. D. Ion-Exchange Resins: A Retrospective from Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 2009, 48(1), 388–398. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie801242v>
2. Chi, Y. Sulfonic Acid Based Cation-Exchange Resin: A Novel Proton Source for Organic Synthesis. *Synthesis* 2008, 2008(2), 185–187. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2007-990950>
3. Nuriddinova D., Yusupov F., Xursandov B. Study of the properties of sulfonic cation exchanger. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 2021, 264, 01025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202126401025>.
4. Nesterenko, P. N.; Kebets, P. A.; Volgin, Y. V. Use of Sulfonated Cation-Exchange Resin Based on Hypercrosslinked Polystyrene for the Separation of Organic Acids. *Journal of Analytical Chemistry*, 2001, 56, 715–720. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016777409132>.
5. Singh A.V., Sharma N.K., Rathore A.S. Synthesis, Characterization and Applications of a New Cation Exchanger Tamarind Sulphonic Acid (TSA) Resin. *Environ. Technol.* 2012, 33(4–6), 473–480. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2011.579184>
6. Badia J. H., Soto R., Ramírez E., Bingué R., Fité C., Iborra M., Tejero J. Role of Ion-Exchange Resins in Hydrogenation Reactions. *Catalysts* 2023, 13(3), 624. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal13030624>
7. Gelbard, G. Organic Synthesis by Catalysis with Ion-Exchange Resins. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 2005, 44(22), 8468–8498. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie0580405>
8. Khayrulla Pulatov, Rano Nazirova, Umida Sharipova, Alisher Yuldashev, Aziza Usmonova, Shakhriyor Sattorov and Yorkinjon Ergashev. Research new type of cation-exchange resin for waste water treatment// *E3S Web of Conferences* 497 ICECAE 2024, 02035 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202449702035>
9. A.A.Yuldashev, F.B.Igitov, T.T.Tursunov, Kh.L.Pulatov Obtaining of polycondensation type anion-exchange polymer, *Journal of Advanced research in dynamical and control systems*, Special issue, 7, pp.2125-2132, (2020)
10. Son Won-Keun, Kim Sang Hern, Kim Tae Il. Determination of the ion exchange capacity of ion exchangers using potentiometric titration // *J. Polym. Sci.*, 2000. - №23. - T.38. - C.3181-3188
11. Kh.L. Pulatov, S.M. Turabjanov, Sorption properties of ion-exchange resins of the polycondensation type, *Universum: Technical sciences*, 12(33), (2016)
12. A.G. Kasikov, N.S. Areshina, I.E. Malts, T.R. Zinkevich, M.A. Mikhailenko, Sorption purification of solutions of copper-nickel production using ion exchangers "Purolite", *Sorption and chromatographic processes*, 5, 11, pp.689-693 (2004)
13. Kh.L.Pulatov, S.M.Turabjanov. Investigation of the possibility of obtaining ion exchangers for wastewater treatment based on secondary products of chemical enterprises, *Chemical Industry*, 5, pp. 231-235 (2017)
14. A.A.Yuldashev, Sh.A.Mutalov and etc. Weakly basic anion-exchange polymers, *Chemistry and chemical technology*, 2, pp. 31-33 (2018).
15. Yadav G. D., Kulkarni H. B. Ion exchange resin catalysis in synthesis // *React. and Funct. Polym.*, 2000. - №2. - T.44. - C.153-165.
16. Rajindar Singh, Development of Hybrid Processes for High Purity Water Production, *Emerging Membrane Technology for Sustainable Water Treatment*, Chapter 13, pp. 327 357, (2016)

17. Khayrulla Pulatov, Tulkun Tursunov, Rano Nazirova, Umida Sharipova, Alisher Yuldashev, Nigora Mukhtarova. Obtaining phosphoric cation-exchange resin for waste water treatment// AIP Conference Proceedings 2432, 050060 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090584>.
18. Dąbrowski, A.; Hubicki, Z.; Podkościelny, P.; Robens, E. Selective Removal of the Heavy Metal Ions from Waters and Industrial Wastewaters by Ion-Exchange Method. *Chemosphere* 2004, 56(2), 91–106. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2004.03.006>
19. Serebrii T.G., Vlasenko N.V., Kochkin Yu.N., Strizhak P.E. *Catalytic Properties of Various Types of Sulfonated Cation-Exchange Resins in the Synthesis of Isopropyl Tert-Butyl Ether. Theoretical and Experimental Chemistry*, 2015, 51(2), 127–132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11237-015-9407-9>.
20. Mukhamediev M.G., Bekchanov D. Zh., Juraev M.M., Lieberzeit P., Gafurova D.A. *A New Sulfonic Acid Cation-Exchange Resin Based on Polyvinyl Chloride and Its Evaluation in Water Softening. Russian Journal of Applied Chemistry*, 2021, 94, 1594–1601. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1070427221120041>.